

On the Forcing Semantics for Monoidal t -norm Based Logic¹

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Abstract: *MTL*-algebras are algebraic structures for the Esteva-Godo monoidal t -norm based logic (*MTL*), a many-valued propositional calculus that formalizes the structure of the real interval $[0, 1]$, induced by a left-continuous t -norm. Given a complete *MTL*-algebra \mathcal{X} , we define the weak forcing value $|\varphi|_{\mathcal{X}}$ and the forcing value $[\varphi]_{\mathcal{X}}$, for any formula φ of *MTL* in \mathcal{X} . We establish some arithmetical properties of $|\cdot|_{\mathcal{X}}$ and $[\cdot]_{\mathcal{X}}$, and prove the equality $[\varphi]_{\mathcal{X}} = \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{X}}$, where $\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{X}}$ is the truth value of φ in \mathcal{X} .

Key Words: *MTL* logic, *MTL*-algebras, forcing semantics

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1 Introduction

In many cases, the approximate reasoning operates with a conjunction which generalize the one in the classical logic. The triangular norm (t -norm) is a good candidate for modelling this kind of conjunction [Bělohlavek 2002, Gottwald 2005, Klement et.al. 2000].

The structure defined by a continuous t -norm on the interval $[0, 1]$ constitutes the base for Hajek's Basic Logic (*BL*) [Hájek 1998a, Hájek 1998b] and for *BL*-algebras, the structures canonically associated to *BL* [Hájek and Ševčík 2004, Cintula and Hájek 2006].

More generally, the Esteva-Godo logic *MTL* and *MTL*-algebras correspond to the left-continuous t -norms and their residua [Esteva and Godo 2001]. The completeness theorems for *MTL* (and for the derived logical systems) concerns with the usual algebraic semantic [Esteva et.al. 2002]. Another kind of semantics for *MTL* (named Kripke semantics) are discussed in [Montagna and Ono 2002,

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Montagna and Sacchetti 2004]. The Kripke semantics for MTL are based on the notion of r -forcing.

The concept of truth value is the usual way to evaluate the formulas of MTL . For a formula φ of MTL , the truth value $\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{X}}$ of φ is defined in an MTL -algebra \mathcal{X} .

In this paper we shall adopt an alternative point of view: for any formula φ of MTL and for any complete MTL -algebra \mathcal{X} , we define the weak forcing value $|\varphi|_{\mathcal{X}}$ and the forcing value $[\varphi]_{\mathcal{X}}$ of φ in \mathcal{X} . These two semantics correspond to the notions of forcing and r -forcing studied in [Montagna and Ono 2002, Montagna and Sacchetti 2004]. Thus, instead of talking about "the formula φ is valid in a Kripke model", we calculate $|\varphi|_{\mathcal{X}}$ or $[\varphi]_{\mathcal{X}}$.

Section 2 contains some basic notions and results on residuated lattices and MTL -algebras. Some elements of syntax and semantic of MTL are recalled in Section 3.

In Section 4 we establish a lot of properties regarding the behaviour of the weak forcing value w.r.t. some types of formulas of MTL . In Section 5 we continue to study the behaviour of $|\cdot|_{\mathcal{X}}$ w.r.t. some formulas of MTL (especially the axioms of MTL) and compare the truth value semantics with the weak forcing semantic.

The main result of this paper (Theorem 19) shows that $[\varphi]_{\mathcal{X}} = \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{X}}$, for any formula φ of MTL and for any complete MTL -algebra \mathcal{X} . The equality $[\cdot]_{\mathcal{X}} = \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{X}}$ improves the relationship between Kripke-style semantic and algebraic semantic studied in [Montagna and Ono 2002, Montagna and Sacchetti 2004].

Section 7 contains some suggestions for further research on $|\cdot|_{\mathcal{X}}$ and $[\cdot]_{\mathcal{X}}$ in the framework of predicate logic $MTL\forall$ and of some non-commutative fuzzy logics associated to MTL and $MTL\forall$.

2 MTL -algebras

A *residuated lattice* is a structure $\mathcal{A} = (A, \vee, \wedge, \cdot, \rightarrow, 0, 1)$ equipped with an order \leq satisfying the following:

- i) $(A, \vee, \wedge, 0, 1)$ is a bounded lattice;
- ii) $(A, \cdot, 1)$ is a commutative monoid;
- iii) For any $a, b, c \in A$, $a \cdot b \leq c$ iff $a \leq b \rightarrow c$.

We shall write ab instead of $a \cdot b$.

In a residuated lattice \mathcal{A} , the *negation* $\bar{\cdot}$ is introduced by $\bar{a} = a \rightarrow 0$, for any $a \in A$.

Lemma 1. [Bělohávek 2002] *Let \mathcal{A} be a residuated lattice. Then, for all $a, b, c \in A$, the following hold:*

- (1) $a \leq b$ iff $a \rightarrow b = 1$;
- (2) $a \cdot 0 = 0$;
- (3) $1 \rightarrow a = a$;
- (4) $ab \leq a$;
- (5) $a(a \rightarrow b) \leq b$;
- (6) $a \rightarrow (b \rightarrow c) = b \rightarrow (a \rightarrow c) = ab \rightarrow c$;
- (7) If $b \leq c$, then $a \rightarrow b \leq a \rightarrow c$ and $c \rightarrow a \leq b \rightarrow a$;
- (8) If $a \leq b$, then $ac \leq bc$;
- (9) $a \rightarrow a = 1$.

Lemma 2. [Bělohávek 2002] Let \mathcal{A} be a residuated lattice. Then, for all elements $a \in A$ and $\{a_i\}_{i \in I} \subseteq A$, the following hold:

- (1) $(\bigvee_{i \in I} a_i) \rightarrow a = \bigwedge_{i \in I} (a_i \rightarrow a)$;
- (2) $a \rightarrow (\bigwedge_{i \in I} a_i) = \bigwedge_{i \in I} (a \rightarrow a_i)$;
- (3) $a(\bigvee_{i \in I} a_i) = \bigvee_{i \in I} aa_i$;
- (4) $\bigvee_{i \in I} (a \rightarrow a_i) \leq a \rightarrow (\bigvee_{i \in I} a_i)$;
- (5) $\bigvee_{i \in I} (a_i \rightarrow a) \leq (\bigwedge_{i \in I} a_i) \rightarrow a$.

An *MTL-algebra* [Esteva and Godo 2001] is a residuated lattice \mathcal{A} such that, for all $a, b \in A$, we have

$$(iv) (a \rightarrow b) \vee (b \rightarrow a) = 1.$$

Example. A *t-norm* is a binary operation $*$ on the interval $[0, 1]$ which is associative, commutative, non-decreasing in the both arguments and the identity $a * 1 = a$ holds. If $*$ is a left-continuous *t-norm*, then $([0, 1], \vee, \wedge, *, \rightarrow, 0, 1)$ is an *MTL-algebra*, where the residuum operation \rightarrow on $[0, 1]$ is defined by

$$a \rightarrow b = \bigvee \{c \mid a * c \leq b\}.$$

This structure will be called a *standard MTL-algebra*.

Any totally-ordered residuated lattice \mathcal{A} is an *MTL-algebra*. In this case, \mathcal{A} will be called an *MTL-chain*. By [Cintula and Hájek 2006], any *MTL-algebra* is isomorphic to a subdirect product of *MTL-chains*.

Lemma 3. ([Bělohávek 2002], Theorem 2.34) *If \mathcal{A} is a residuated lattice, then the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (i) \mathcal{A} is an *MTL*-algebra;
- (ii) For all $a, b, c \in A$, $a \rightarrow (b \vee c) = (a \rightarrow b) \vee (a \rightarrow c)$;
- (iii) For all $a, b, c \in A$, $(b \wedge c) \rightarrow a = (b \rightarrow a) \vee (c \rightarrow a)$.

3 Monoidal *t*-norm based logic

In this section we shall recall some basic notions of the monoidal *t*-norm based logic (*MTL*) (see [Esteva and Godo 2001, Esteva et.al. 2002]).

The language of *MTL* has the following primitive symbols:

- denumerable many propositional variables (V will denote the set of propositional variables);
- the connectives $\vee, \wedge, \odot, \rightarrow$;
- the symbol \perp ;
- the parenthesis $(,)$.

The set *Form* of formulas of *MTL* is defined as usual. Let us denote $\top = 1 \rightarrow \perp$. We list the axioms of *MTL*:

- (A1) $(\varphi \rightarrow \psi) \rightarrow ((\psi \rightarrow \chi) \rightarrow (\varphi \rightarrow \chi))$;
- (A2) $\varphi \odot \psi \rightarrow \psi$;
- (A3) $\varphi \odot \psi \rightarrow \psi \odot \varphi$;
- (A4) $\varphi \wedge \psi \rightarrow \varphi$;
- (A5) $\varphi \wedge \psi \rightarrow \psi \wedge \varphi$;
- (A6) $\varphi \odot (\varphi \rightarrow \psi) \rightarrow (\varphi \wedge \psi)$;
- (A7) $(\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \chi)) \rightarrow ((\varphi \odot \psi) \rightarrow \chi)$;
- (A8) $((\varphi \odot \psi) \rightarrow \chi) \rightarrow (\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \chi))$;
- (A9) $(\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \chi)) \rightarrow (((\psi \rightarrow \varphi) \rightarrow \chi) \rightarrow \chi)$;
- (A10) $\perp \rightarrow \varphi$.

Modus-ponens is the only rule of inference of *MTL*: $\frac{\varphi, \varphi \rightarrow \psi}{\psi}$.

The notion of provable formula is defined as usual. We denote by $\vdash \varphi$ that the formula φ is provable in *MTL*.

Let Σ be a subset of the set of axioms (A1)-(A10). If φ is a formula of *MTL*, then we denote by $\vdash_{\Sigma} \varphi$ that φ can be derived from Σ by using modus-ponens; if Σ is the set of all axioms (A1)-(A10), then $\vdash_{\Sigma} \varphi$ means that $\vdash \varphi$.

Let $\mathcal{X} = (X, \vee, \wedge, \cdot, \rightarrow, 0, 1)$ be an *MTL*-algebra. An *evaluation* of *MTL* in \mathcal{X} is a function $e : V \rightarrow X$. Any evaluation $e : V \rightarrow X$ can be uniquely extended to a function $\hat{e} : Form \rightarrow X$ with the property that for all $\varphi, \psi \in Form$ we have:

- (a) $\hat{e}(\varphi) = e(\varphi)$, if $\varphi \in V$;
- (b) $\hat{e}(\perp) = 0$;
- (c) $\hat{e}(\varphi \vee \psi) = \hat{e}(\varphi) \vee \hat{e}(\psi)$;
- (d) $\hat{e}(\varphi \wedge \psi) = \hat{e}(\varphi) \wedge \hat{e}(\psi)$;
- (e) $\hat{e}(\varphi \odot \psi) = \hat{e}(\varphi) \cdot \hat{e}(\psi)$;
- (f) $\hat{e}(\varphi \rightarrow \psi) = \hat{e}(\varphi) \rightarrow \hat{e}(\psi)$.

The *truth value* $\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{X}}$ of a formula φ in \mathcal{X} is defined by:

$$\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{X}} = \bigwedge \{ \hat{e}(\varphi) \mid e \text{ is an evaluation in } \mathcal{X} \}.$$

4 Weak forcing value of a formula of *MTL*

In this section we shall define the weak forcing value $|\varphi|_{\mathcal{X}}$ of a formula φ of *MTL* in a complete *MTL*-algebra \mathcal{X} . Besides the truth value $\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{X}}$ of φ in \mathcal{X} , $|\varphi|_{\mathcal{X}}$ constitutes an alternative to evaluate the formula φ in \mathcal{X} . The weak forcing value is a refinement of the notion of validity in a Kripke model (in the sense of [Montagna and Ono 2002, Montagna and Sacchetti 2004]).

We fix a complete *MTL*-algebra $\mathcal{X} = (X, \vee, \wedge, \cdot, \rightarrow, 0, 1)$.

Definition 4. An \mathcal{X} -valued weak forcing property is a function

$$f : (V \cup \{\perp\}) \times X \rightarrow X$$

such that the following conditions hold:

- (i) If $\varphi \in V$ and $x, y \in X$, then $x \leq y$ implies $f(\varphi, y) \leq f(\varphi, x)$;
- (ii) $f(\perp, 1) = 0$.

Definition 5. Let f be an \mathcal{X} -valued weak forcing property. For any $\varphi \in Form$ and $x \in X$, we define, by induction, the element $[\varphi]_x^f$ of X :

- (1) $[\varphi]_x^f = f(\varphi, x)$, if $\varphi \in V$;
- (2) $[\perp]_x^f = \bar{x}$;
- (3) If $\varphi = \alpha \vee \beta$, then $[\varphi]_x^f = [\alpha]_x^f \vee [\beta]_x^f$;
- (4) If $\varphi = \alpha \wedge \beta$, then $[\varphi]_x^f = [\alpha]_x^f \wedge [\beta]_x^f$;
- (5) If $\varphi = \alpha \odot \beta$, then $[\varphi]_x^f = \bigvee_{y,z \in X} ((x \rightarrow yz) [\alpha]_y^f [\beta]_z^f)$;
- (6) If $\varphi = \alpha \rightarrow \beta$, then $[\varphi]_x^f = \bigwedge_{y \in X} ([\alpha]_y^f \rightarrow [\beta]_{xy}^f)$.

For simplicity, we shall usually write $[\varphi]_x$ instead of $[\varphi]_x^f$.

Definition 6. The **weak forcing value** $|\varphi|_{\mathcal{X}}$ of a formula φ in \mathcal{X} is defined by

$$|\varphi|_{\mathcal{X}} = \bigwedge \{ [\varphi]_1^f \mid f \text{ is an } \mathcal{X}\text{-valued weak forcing property} \}.$$

Lemma 7. Let f be an \mathcal{X} -valued weak forcing property. For any formula φ of MTL and $y \leq x$ in X , we have $[\varphi]_x \leq [\varphi]_y$.

Proof. We proceed by induction on the complexity of φ . We treat only the case $\varphi = \alpha \rightarrow \beta$. If $y \leq x$, then $yz \leq xz$, hence, by induction hypothesis, we have $[\beta]_{xz} \leq [\beta]_{yz}$, for all $z \in X$. Then, by Lemma 1, (7), we get

$$[\varphi]_x = \bigwedge_{z \in X} ([\alpha]_z \rightarrow [\beta]_{xz}) \leq \bigwedge_{z \in X} ([\alpha]_z \rightarrow [\beta]_{yz}) = [\varphi]_y.$$

Remark. By Lemma 7, $[\varphi]_1 \leq [\varphi]_x$, for any $x \in X$.

In what follows, we emphasize the behaviour of $[\cdot]^f$ and $|\cdot|_{\mathcal{X}}$ w.r.t. some formulas of MTL.

Proposition 8. Let f be an \mathcal{X} -valued weak forcing property. For all formulas φ, ψ, χ of MTL and $x, y, a, b, c, p, q, t \in X$, the following hold:

- (1) $[\varphi \rightarrow \varphi]_x = 1$;
- (2) $[\top]_x = 1$;
- (3) $[\psi]_x \leq [\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_x$;
- (4) $[\varphi]_x \cdot [\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_y \leq [\psi]_{xy}$;
- (5) $[\varphi]_x \cdot [\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_x \leq [\psi]_{x^2}$;
- (6) $[\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_a \cdot [\psi \rightarrow \chi]_b \leq [\varphi]_c \rightarrow [\chi]_{abc}$;
- (7) $[\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_x \leq [\psi \rightarrow \chi]_y \rightarrow [\varphi \rightarrow \chi]_{xy}$;
- (8) $[\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \chi)]_x = \bigwedge_{u,v \in X} ([\varphi]_u [\psi]_v \rightarrow [\chi]_{xuv})$;

- (9) $[\varphi \odot \psi \rightarrow \chi]_x = \bigwedge_{p,q,t \in X} ((t \rightarrow pq) [\varphi]_p [\psi]_q \rightarrow [\chi]_{tx});$
(10) $[\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \chi)]_x = [\psi \rightarrow (\varphi \rightarrow \chi)]_x;$
(11) $[(\varphi \rightarrow \psi) \rightarrow ((\psi \rightarrow \chi) \rightarrow (\varphi \rightarrow \chi))]_x = 1;$
(12) $[(\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \chi)) \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow (\varphi \rightarrow \chi))]_x = 1;$
(13) $[\varphi \odot \psi \rightarrow \chi]_x \leq [\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \chi)]_x;$
(14) $[(\varphi \odot \psi \rightarrow \chi) \rightarrow (\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \chi))]_x = 1;$
(15) $[(\varphi \rightarrow \psi) \wedge (\varphi \rightarrow \chi)]_x = [\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \wedge \chi)]_x;$
(16) $[\varphi \odot (\psi \vee \chi)]_x = [(\varphi \odot \psi) \vee (\varphi \odot \chi)]_x.$

Proof.

(1) By Lemma 7, $[\varphi \rightarrow \varphi]_x \geq [\varphi \rightarrow \varphi]_1 = \bigwedge_{u \in X} ([\varphi]_u \rightarrow [\varphi]_u) = 1.$

(2) Since \top is $\perp \rightarrow \perp$, by (1) we obtain $[\top]_x = 1.$

(3) By Lemma 1, (4), and Lemma 7, $[\psi]_x \leq [\psi]_{ux}$, for each $u \in X$. Then, by Lemma 1, (1), (7), $[\psi]_x \leq [\varphi]_u \rightarrow [\psi]_x \leq [\varphi]_u \rightarrow [\psi]_{ux}$ for each $u \in X$. Hence $[\psi]_x \leq \bigwedge_{u \in X} ([\varphi]_u \rightarrow [\psi]_{ux}) = [\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_x.$

(4) According to Lemma 1, (5), we have

$$[\varphi]_x \cdot [\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_y = [\varphi]_x \cdot \bigwedge_{u \in X} ([\varphi]_u \rightarrow [\psi]_{yu}) \leq [\varphi]_x \cdot ([\varphi]_x \rightarrow [\psi]_{xy}) \leq [\psi]_{xy}.$$

(5) By (4).

(6) Using (4), we have $[\varphi]_c \cdot [\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_a \cdot [\psi \rightarrow \chi]_b \leq [\psi]_{ac} \cdot [\psi \rightarrow \chi]_b \leq [\chi]_{abc}$, so, the inequality $[\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_a \cdot [\psi \rightarrow \chi]_b \leq [\varphi]_c \rightarrow [\chi]_{abc}$ follows.

(7) According to (6), for each $u \in X$ we have $[\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_x \cdot [\psi \rightarrow \chi]_y \leq [\varphi]_u \rightarrow [\chi]_{uxy}$, so $[\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_x \cdot [\psi \rightarrow \chi]_y \leq \bigwedge_{u \in X} ([\varphi]_u \rightarrow [\chi]_{uxy}) = [\varphi \rightarrow \chi]_{xy}$. Hence $[\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_x \leq [\psi \rightarrow \chi]_y \rightarrow [\varphi \rightarrow \chi]_{xy}.$

(8) Applying the clause (6) of Definition 5, Lemma 2, (2), and Lemma 1, (6), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} [\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \chi)]_x &= \bigwedge_{u \in X} ([\varphi]_u \rightarrow [\psi \rightarrow \chi]_{xu}) = \\ &= \bigwedge_{u \in X} ([\varphi]_u \rightarrow \bigwedge_{v \in X} ([\psi]_v \rightarrow [\chi]_{xuv})) = \\ &= \bigwedge_{u,v \in X} ([\varphi]_u [\psi]_v \rightarrow [\chi]_{xuv}). \end{aligned}$$

(9) We apply the clauses (6) and (5) of Definition 5 and Lemma 2, (1), and we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} [\varphi \odot \psi \rightarrow \chi]_x &= \bigwedge_{t \in X} ([\varphi \odot \psi]_t \rightarrow [\chi]_{tx}) = \\ &= \bigwedge_{t \in X} ((\bigvee_{p,q \in X} (t \rightarrow pq) [\varphi]_p [\psi]_q) \rightarrow [\chi]_{tx}) = \end{aligned}$$

$$= \bigwedge_{p,q,t \in X} ((t \rightarrow pq)[\varphi]_p [\psi]_q \rightarrow [\chi]_{tx}).$$

(10) By (8).

(11) By (8), Lemma 7 and (6) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} [(\varphi \rightarrow \psi) \rightarrow ((\psi \rightarrow \chi) \rightarrow (\varphi \rightarrow \chi))]_x &= \\ &= \bigwedge_{u,v \in X} ([\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_u [\psi \rightarrow \chi]_v \rightarrow \bigwedge_{w \in X} ([\varphi]_w \rightarrow [\chi]_{xuvw})) = \\ &= \bigwedge_{u,v,w \in X} ([\varphi]_w [\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_u [\psi \rightarrow \chi]_v \rightarrow [\chi]_{xuvw}) \geq \\ &\geq \bigwedge_{u,v,w \in X} ([\varphi]_w [\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_u [\psi \rightarrow \chi]_v \rightarrow [\chi]_{uvw}) = 1. \end{aligned}$$

(12) Applying Lemma 7 and (10), we get

$$\begin{aligned} [(\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \chi)) \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow (\varphi \rightarrow \chi))]_x &= \\ &= \bigwedge_{u \in X} ([\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \chi)]_u \rightarrow [\psi \rightarrow (\varphi \rightarrow \chi)]_{ux}) \geq \\ &\geq \bigwedge_{u \in X} ([\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \chi)]_u \rightarrow [\psi \rightarrow (\varphi \rightarrow \chi)]_u) = 1. \end{aligned}$$

(13) Let $u, v \in X$. By (9), $[\varphi \odot \psi \rightarrow \chi]_x \leq [\varphi]_u [\psi]_v \rightarrow [\chi]_{xuv}$, hence, by (8), we get $[\varphi \odot \psi \rightarrow \chi]_x \leq \bigwedge_{u,v \in X} ([\varphi]_u [\psi]_v \rightarrow [\chi]_{xuv}) = [\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \chi)]_x$.

(14) Similar to (12).

(15) We have the following

$$\begin{aligned} [(\varphi \rightarrow \psi) \wedge (\varphi \rightarrow \chi)]_x &= [\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_x \wedge [\varphi \rightarrow \chi]_x = \\ &= \bigwedge_{y \in X} ([\varphi]_y \rightarrow [\psi]_{xy}) \wedge \bigwedge_{y \in X} ([\varphi]_y \rightarrow [\chi]_{xy}) = \\ &= \bigwedge_{y \in X} (([\varphi]_y \rightarrow [\psi]_{xy}) \wedge ([\varphi]_y \rightarrow [\chi]_{xy})) = \\ &= \bigwedge_{y \in X} ([\varphi]_y \rightarrow ([\psi]_{xy} \wedge [\chi]_{xy})) = \bigwedge_{y \in X} ([\varphi]_y \rightarrow [\psi \wedge \chi]_{xy}) = \\ &= [\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \wedge \chi)]_x. \end{aligned}$$

(16) We can write

$$\begin{aligned} [(\varphi \odot \psi) \vee (\varphi \odot \chi)]_x &= [\varphi \odot \psi]_x \vee [\varphi \odot \chi]_x = \\ &= (\bigvee_{y,z \in X} (x \rightarrow yz)[\varphi]_y [\psi]_z) \vee (\bigvee_{y,z \in X} (x \rightarrow yz)[\varphi]_y [\chi]_z) = \\ &= \bigvee_{y,z \in X} (((x \rightarrow yz)[\varphi]_y [\psi]_z) \vee ((x \rightarrow yz)[\varphi]_y [\chi]_z)) = \\ &= \bigvee_{y \in X} (x \rightarrow yz)[\varphi]_y ([\psi]_z \vee [\chi]_z) = \\ &= \bigvee_{y,z \in X} (x \rightarrow yz) [\varphi]_y [\psi \vee \chi]_z = [\varphi \odot (\psi \vee \chi)]_x. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 9. For any formulas φ , ψ and χ of MTL, the following hold:

- (1) $|\varphi \rightarrow \varphi|_{\mathcal{X}} = 1$;
- (2) $|\top|_{\mathcal{X}} = 1$;
- (3) $|\psi|_{\mathcal{X}} \leq |\varphi \rightarrow \psi|_{\mathcal{X}}$;
- (4) $|\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \chi)|_{\mathcal{X}} = |\psi \rightarrow (\varphi \rightarrow \chi)|_{\mathcal{X}}$;
- (5) $|(\varphi \rightarrow \psi) \rightarrow ((\psi \rightarrow \chi) \rightarrow (\varphi \rightarrow \chi))|_{\mathcal{X}} = 1$;
- (6) $|(\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \chi)) \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow (\varphi \rightarrow \chi))|_{\mathcal{X}} = 1$;

$$(7) |(\varphi \odot \psi \rightarrow \chi) \rightarrow (\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \chi))|_{\mathcal{X}} = 1.$$

Corollary 10. *If $|\varphi|_{\mathcal{X}} = |\varphi \rightarrow \psi|_{\mathcal{X}} = 1$, then $|\psi|_{\mathcal{X}} = 1$.*

Remark. Assume that Σ is the set of axioms (A1), (A3), (A4), (A8), (A10) and φ is a formula of *MTL*. By Corollaries 9 and 10, if $\vdash_{\Sigma} \varphi$, then $|\varphi|_{\mathcal{X}} = 1$.

Proposition 11. *Let f be an \mathcal{X} -valued weak forcing property. For any formula φ of *MTL* and $x, y \in X$, we have:*

- (1) $[\neg\varphi]_x = \bigwedge_{y \in X} (xy[\varphi]_y)^{-} = x \rightarrow \bigwedge_{y \in X} (y[\varphi]_y)^{-}$;
- (2) $xy[\neg\varphi]_x[\varphi]_y = 0$;
- (3) $[\varphi]_x \leq [\neg\neg\varphi]_x$;
- (4) $[\neg\varphi]_x = [\neg\neg\neg\varphi]_x$;
- (5) $[\neg(\varphi \vee \psi)]_x = [\neg\varphi \wedge \neg\psi]_x$;
- (6) $[\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_x \leq [\neg\psi \rightarrow \neg\varphi]_x$;
- (7) $[\varphi \rightarrow \neg\psi]_x \leq [\psi \rightarrow \neg\varphi]_x$;
- (8) $x[\varphi \odot \neg\varphi]_x = 0$;
- (9) $[\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \odot \neg\psi)]_x \leq [\neg\varphi]_x$.

Proof.

$$(1) [\neg\varphi]_x = \bigwedge_{y \in X} ([\varphi]_y \rightarrow [\perp]_{xy}) = \bigwedge_{y \in X} ([\varphi]_y \rightarrow \overline{xy}) = \bigwedge_{y \in X} (xy[\varphi]_y)^{-}.$$

In a similar way we get $[\neg\varphi]_x = x \rightarrow \bigwedge_{y \in X} (y[\varphi]_y)^{-}$.

$$(2) \text{ By (1), for any } y \in X, \text{ we have } [\neg\varphi]_x \leq (xy[\varphi]_y)^{-}, \text{ hence } xy[\neg\varphi]_x[\varphi]_y = 0.$$

$$(3) \text{ Let } y \in X. \text{ By (2), } xy[\varphi]_x[\neg\varphi]_y = 0, \text{ hence } x[\varphi]_x \leq (y[\neg\varphi]_y)^{-}.$$

Thus $x[\varphi]_x \leq \bigwedge_{y \in X} (y[\neg\varphi]_y)^{-}$, so $[\varphi]_x \leq x \rightarrow \bigwedge_{y \in X} (y[\neg\varphi]_y)^{-} = [\neg\neg\varphi]_x$.

(4) Let $y \in X$. By (3) and (2) we get $xy[\varphi]_y[\neg\neg\neg\varphi]_x \leq xy[\neg\neg\varphi]_y[\neg\neg\neg\varphi]_x = 0$, therefore $x[\neg\neg\neg\varphi]_x \leq (y[\varphi]_y)^{-}$. Thus $x[\neg\neg\neg\varphi]_x \leq \bigwedge_{y \in X} (y[\varphi]_y)^{-}$, hence $[\neg\neg\neg\varphi]_x \leq x \rightarrow \bigwedge_{y \in X} (y[\varphi]_y)^{-} = [\neg\varphi]_x$. The converse implication follows by (3).

(5) We have

$$\begin{aligned} [\neg\varphi \wedge \neg\psi]_x &= [\neg\varphi]_x \wedge [\neg\psi]_x = \bigwedge_{y \in X} (xy[\varphi]_y)^{-} \wedge \bigwedge_{y \in X} (xy[\psi]_y)^{-} = \\ &= \bigwedge_{y \in X} ((xy[\varphi]_y)^{-} \wedge (xy[\psi]_y)^{-}) = \\ &= \bigwedge_{y \in X} (xy[\varphi]_y \vee xy[\psi]_y)^{-} = \bigwedge_{y \in X} (xy([\varphi]_y \vee [\psi]_y)^{-}) = \\ &= \bigwedge_{y \in X} (xy[\varphi \vee \psi]_y)^{-} = [\neg(\varphi \wedge \psi)]_x. \end{aligned}$$

(6) Let $y, z \in X$. According to Proposition 8, (4), $[\varphi]_y[\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_x \leq [\psi]_{xy}$, hence, by (3), we get $[\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_x \cdot [\neg\psi]_z \cdot xyz \cdot [\varphi]_y \leq xyz \cdot [\psi]_{xy}[\neg\psi]_z = 0$. Then, for each $y \in X$, we have $[\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_x[\neg\psi]_z \leq (xyz[\varphi]_y)^-$, therefore $[\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_x[\neg\psi]_z \leq \bigwedge_{y \in X} (xyz[\varphi]_y)^- = [\neg\varphi]_{xz}$.

It follows that $[\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_x \leq [\neg\psi]_z \rightarrow [\neg\varphi]_{xz}$. This last inequality holds for each $z \in X$, therefore $[\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_x \leq \bigwedge_{z \in X} ([\neg\psi]_z \rightarrow [\neg\varphi]_{xz}) = [\neg\psi \rightarrow \neg\varphi]_x$.

(7) Similar to (6).

(8) According to Definition 5, (5), and the previous equality (2), one obtains $x[\varphi \odot \neg\varphi]_x = x \bigvee_{y, z \in X} (x \rightarrow yz)[\varphi]_y[\neg\varphi]_z = \bigvee_{y, z \in X} x(x \rightarrow yz)[\varphi]_y[\neg\varphi]_z \leq \bigvee_{y, z \in X} yz[\varphi]_y[\neg\varphi]_z = 0$.

(9) Let $y \in X$. By Proposition 8, (4), and the previous equality (8), we get $[\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \odot \neg\psi)]_x \cdot xy[\varphi]_y \leq xy[\psi \odot \neg\psi]_{xy} = 0$. Thus $[\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \odot \neg\psi)]_x \leq (xy[\varphi]_y)^-$, for any $y \in X$, hence $[\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \odot \neg\psi)]_x \leq \bigwedge_{y \in X} (xy[\varphi]_y)^- = [\neg\varphi]_x$.

5 The behaviour of $|\cdot|_{\mathcal{X}}$ w.r.t. some formulas of *MTL*

In this section we will compare the two kinds of semantics: truth value and weak forcing. A formula φ of *MTL* is valid in the weak forcing semantic iff $[\varphi]_1^f = 1$, for any \mathcal{X} -valued weak forcing property.

In the following we will analyze the behaviour of $|\cdot|_{\mathcal{X}}$ w.r.t. the axioms of *MTL* and some other formulas. We will prove that some axioms are valid via the new kind of semantics, while others are not valid (in this latter case we will provide a counterexample of a weak forcing property f for which $[\varphi]_1^f \neq 1$).

This analysis is very important in providing the similarities and the differences between the two semantics $|\cdot|_{\mathcal{X}}$ and $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{X}}$.

(A1) $(\varphi \rightarrow \psi) \rightarrow ((\psi \rightarrow \chi) \rightarrow (\varphi \rightarrow \chi))$

By Corollary 9, (5), this axiom is valid w.r.t. the weak forcing semantic.

(A2) $\varphi \odot \psi \rightarrow \psi$

Let us consider $\mathcal{X} = L_3 = \{0, \frac{1}{2}, 1\}$ with the canonical structure of *MV*₃-algebra ².

² An *MV-algebra* is a structure $(A, \oplus, \odot, ^-, 0, 1)$, where \oplus and \odot are binary operations,

$^-$ is unary and 0,1 are constants, satisfying the following axioms:

a) $(A, \oplus, 0)$ and $(A, \odot, 1)$ are commutative monoids,

b) $x \odot 0 = 0$ and $x \oplus 1 = 1$, for any $x \in A$,

c) $x^{--} = x$, for any $x \in A$,

Let us consider $p, q \in V$ (some propositional variables) and the weak forcing property f which has the following behaviour w.r.t. p and q :

f	0	$\frac{1}{2}$	1
p	1	1	1
q	1	1	0

We have the followings:

$$[p \odot q]_0^f = \bigvee_{y, z \in L_3} \cdot f(p, y) \cdot f(q, z) = 1$$

$$[p \odot q]_{\frac{1}{2}}^f = \bigvee_{y, z \in L_3} (\frac{1}{2} \rightarrow yz) \cdot f(p, y) \cdot f(q, z) = 1$$

$$[p \odot q]_1^f = \bigvee_{y, z \in L_3} (1 \rightarrow yz) \cdot f(p, y) \cdot f(q, z) = \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[p \odot q \rightarrow q]_1^f = \bigwedge_{x \in L_3} ([p \odot q]_x^f \rightarrow f(q, x)) = (1 \rightarrow 1) \wedge (1 \rightarrow 1) \wedge (\frac{1}{2} \rightarrow 0) = \frac{1}{2}$$

Thus $[p \odot q \rightarrow q]_1^f = \frac{1}{2} \neq 1$ which prove that (A2) is not valid w.r.t. the new semantics.

(A3) $\varphi \odot \psi \rightarrow \psi \odot \varphi$

Let f be a weak forcing property. Using Lemma 1, (9), we get:

$$\begin{aligned} [\varphi \odot \psi \rightarrow \psi \odot \varphi]_1^f &= \bigwedge_{t \in L_3} ([\varphi \odot \psi]_t^f \rightarrow [\psi \odot \varphi]_t^f) = \\ &= \bigwedge_{t \in L_3} [(\bigvee_{y, z \in L_3} (t \rightarrow yz) [\varphi]_y^f [\psi]_z^f) \rightarrow (\bigvee_{y, z \in L_3} (t \rightarrow yz) [\varphi]_y^f [\psi]_z^f)] = 1. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the axiom is valid w.r.t. the weak forcing semantic.

(A4) $\varphi \wedge \psi \rightarrow \varphi$

Let f be a weak forcing property.

By Lemma 3, (3), and Lemma 1, (9), we have:

$$\begin{aligned} [\varphi \wedge \psi \rightarrow \varphi]_1^f &= \bigwedge_{y \in L_3} ([\varphi \wedge \psi]_y^f \rightarrow [\varphi]_y^f) = \bigwedge_{y \in L_3} (([\varphi]_y^f \wedge [\psi]_y^f) \rightarrow [\varphi]_y^f) = \\ &= \bigwedge_{y \in L_3} (([\varphi]_y^f \rightarrow [\varphi]_y^f) \vee ([\psi]_y^f \rightarrow [\varphi]_y^f)) = \\ &= \bigwedge_{y \in L_3} (1 \vee ([\psi]_y^f \rightarrow [\varphi]_y^f)) = 1. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore this axiom is valid in the new semantics.

d) $(x \oplus y)^- = x^- \odot y^-$, for any $x, y \in A$,

e) $(x \odot y^-) \oplus y = (y \odot x^-) \oplus x$, for any $x, y \in A$.

An MV_3 -algebra is an MV -algebra with the property $x \oplus x \oplus x = x \oplus x$.

Any MV -algebra is an MTL -algebra, where the implication is given by $x \rightarrow y = \bar{x} \oplus y$.

(A5) $\varphi \wedge \psi \rightarrow \psi \wedge \varphi$

Let f be a weak forcing property. Using Lemma 3, (3), Lemma 2, (2), and the definition of an MTL -algebra, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
[\varphi \wedge \psi \rightarrow \psi \wedge \varphi]_1^f &= \bigwedge_{y \in L_3} ([\varphi \wedge \psi]_y^f \rightarrow [\psi \wedge \varphi]_y^f) = \\
&= \bigwedge_{y \in L_3} (([\varphi]_y^f \wedge [\psi]_y^f) \rightarrow ([\psi]_y^f \wedge [\varphi]_y^f)) = \\
&= \bigwedge_{y \in L_3} ([\varphi]_y^f \rightarrow ([\psi]_y^f \wedge [\varphi]_y^f)) \vee ([\psi]_y^f \rightarrow ([\varphi]_y^f \wedge [\psi]_y^f)) = \\
&= \bigwedge_{y \in L_3} ((([\varphi]_y^f \rightarrow [\psi]_y^f) \wedge ([\varphi]_y^f \rightarrow [\varphi]_y^f)) \vee (([\psi]_y^f \rightarrow [\varphi]_y^f) \wedge ([\psi]_y^f \rightarrow [\psi]_y^f))) = \\
&= \bigwedge_{y \in X} ([\varphi]_y^f \rightarrow [\psi]_y^f) \vee ([\psi]_y^f \rightarrow [\varphi]_y^f) = 1
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore this axiom is valid w.r.t. the weak forcing semantic.

(A6) $\varphi \odot (\varphi \rightarrow \psi) \rightarrow (\varphi \rightarrow \psi)$

Let us consider $\mathcal{X} = L_3 = \{0, \frac{1}{2}, 1\}$ with the canonical structure of MV_3 -algebra and let $p, q \in V$ and f be a weak forcing property which has the following behaviour w.r.t. p, q :

f	0	$\frac{1}{2}$	1
p	1	1	1
q	1	1	0

Because $[p \rightarrow q]_x^f = \bigwedge_{y \in L_3} f(p, y) \rightarrow f(q, x \cdot y)$, we obtain $[p \rightarrow q]_0^f = 1$, $[p \rightarrow q]_{\frac{1}{2}}^f = 1$ and $[p \rightarrow q]_1^f = 0$.

We also have the followings:

$$\begin{aligned}
[p \odot (p \rightarrow q)]_0^f &= \bigvee_{t, z \in L_3} f(p, t) \cdot [p \rightarrow q]_z^f = 1 \\
[p \odot (p \rightarrow q)]_{\frac{1}{2}}^f &= \bigvee_{t, z \in L_3} (\frac{1}{2} \rightarrow tz) \cdot f(p, t) \cdot [p \rightarrow q]_z^f = 1 \\
[p \odot (p \rightarrow q)]_1^f &= \bigvee_{t, z \in L_3} (1 \rightarrow tz) \cdot f(p, t) \cdot [p \rightarrow q]_z^f = \frac{1}{2} \\
[p \odot (p \rightarrow q) \rightarrow (p \wedge q)]_1^f &= \bigwedge_{x \in L_3} ([p \odot (p \rightarrow q)]_x^f \rightarrow [p \wedge q]_x^f) = \\
&= \bigwedge_{x \in L_3} ([p \odot (p \rightarrow q)]_x^f \rightarrow (f(p, x) \wedge f(q, x))) = \\
&= [1 \rightarrow (1 \wedge 1)] \wedge [1 \rightarrow (1 \wedge 1)] \wedge [\frac{1}{2} \rightarrow (1 \wedge 0)] = 1 \wedge 1 \wedge \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{2}
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, $[p \odot (p \rightarrow q) \rightarrow (p \wedge q)]_1^f = \frac{1}{2} \neq 1$. This prove that axiom (A6) is not valid w.r.t. the weak forcing semantic.

(A7) $(\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \chi)) \rightarrow ((\varphi \odot \psi) \rightarrow \chi)$

From [Iorgulescu 2004], the set $A = \{0, a, b, c, d, 1\}$ is organized as a lattice as in Figure 1 and as an MTL -algebra \mathcal{A} with the operation \rightarrow and \odot as in the following tables:

\rightarrow	0 a b c d 1
0	1 1 1 1 1 1
a	d 1 1 1 1 1
b	a a 1 1 1 1
c	0 a d 1 d 1
d	a a c c 1 1
1	0 a b c d 1

\odot	0 a b c d 1
0	0 0 0 0 0 0
a	0 0 0 a 0 a
b	0 0 b b b b
c	0 a b c b c
d	0 0 b b d d
1	0 a b c d 1

Let us consider $p, q, r \in V$ and f a weak forcing property with the following behaviour w.r.t. p, q, r :

f	0	a	b	c	d	1
p	1	1	d	d	d	d
q	1	a	a	0	0	0
r	b	0	0	0	0	0

Because $[p \odot q]_x^f = \bigwedge_{y,z \in A} (x \rightarrow yz) \cdot f(p, y) \cdot f(q, z)$, we have $[p \odot q]_0^f = 1$, $[p \odot q]_a^f = d$, $[p \odot q]_b^f = a$, $[p \odot q]_c^f = 0$, $[p \odot q]_d^f = a$ and $[p \odot q]_1^f = 0$. We have the followings:

$$\begin{aligned}
 [(p \odot q) \rightarrow r]_1^f &= \bigwedge_{x \in A} ([p \odot q]_x^f \rightarrow f(r, 1 \cdot x)) = \bigwedge_{x \in A} ([p \odot q]_x^f \rightarrow f(r, x)) = \\
 &= (1 \rightarrow b) \wedge (d \rightarrow 0) \wedge (a \rightarrow 0) \wedge (0 \rightarrow 0) \wedge (a \rightarrow 0) \wedge (0 \rightarrow 0) = a
 \end{aligned}$$

Because $[q \rightarrow r]_x^f = \bigwedge_{y \in A} (f(q, y) \rightarrow f(r, x \cdot y))$, we obtain that $[q \rightarrow r]_x^f = b$, for all $x \in A$. Then, we also have:

$$[p \rightarrow (q \rightarrow p)]_1^f = \bigwedge_{x \in A} (f(p, x) \rightarrow [q \rightarrow r]_x^f) = (1 \rightarrow b) \wedge (d \rightarrow b) = b$$

Thus, $[p \rightarrow (q \rightarrow p)]_1^f \rightarrow [(p \odot q) \rightarrow r]_1^f = b \rightarrow a = a$.

By definition, we have

$$[(p \rightarrow (q \rightarrow r)) \rightarrow ((p \odot q) \rightarrow r)]_1^f = \bigwedge_{x \in A} ([p \rightarrow (q \rightarrow r)]_x^f \rightarrow [(p \odot q) \rightarrow r]_x^f),$$

therefore we have

$$[(p \rightarrow (q \rightarrow r)) \rightarrow ((p \odot q) \rightarrow r)]_1^f \leq [p \rightarrow (q \rightarrow r)]_1^f \rightarrow [(p \odot q) \rightarrow r]_1^f = a.$$

Hence, axiom (A7) is not valid w.r.t. the new kind of semantics.

Figure 1:

$$(A8) \quad ((\varphi \odot \psi) \rightarrow \chi) \rightarrow (\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \chi))$$

By Corollary 9, (7), this axiom is valid w.r.t. the weak forcing semantic.

$$(A9) \quad (\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \chi)) \rightarrow (((\psi \rightarrow \varphi) \rightarrow \chi) \rightarrow \chi)$$

Let us consider $\mathcal{X} = L_3 = \{0, \frac{1}{2}, 1\}$ with the canonical structure of MV_3 -algebra. Let us also consider $p, q, r \in V$, some propositional variables, and f a weak forcing property with the following behaviour w.r.t. p, q, r :

f	0	$\frac{1}{2}$	1
p	0	0	0
q	$\frac{1}{2}$	0	0
r	0	0	0

Because $[q \rightarrow p]_x^f = \bigwedge_{y \in L_3} (f(q, y) \rightarrow f(p, x \cdot y))$, we obtain that $[q \rightarrow p]_0^f = \frac{1}{2}$, $[q \rightarrow p]_{\frac{1}{2}}^f = \frac{1}{2}$ and $[q \rightarrow p]_1^f = \frac{1}{2}$.

We have the followings:

$$\begin{aligned} [p \rightarrow (q \rightarrow r)]_0^f &= \bigwedge_{z \in L_3} (f(p, z) \rightarrow [q \rightarrow r]_0^f) = \bigwedge_{z \in L_3} (0 \rightarrow [q \rightarrow r]_0^f) = 1 \\ [(q \rightarrow p) \rightarrow r]_x^f &= \bigwedge_{y \in L_3} ([q \rightarrow p]_y^f \rightarrow f(r, x \cdot y)) = \bigwedge_{y \in L_3} ([q \rightarrow p]_y^f \rightarrow 0) = \frac{1}{2} \\ [((q \rightarrow p) \rightarrow r) \rightarrow r]_0^f &= \bigwedge_{x \in L_3} ([(q \rightarrow p) \rightarrow r]_x^f \rightarrow f(r, 0)) = \frac{1}{2} \\ [p \rightarrow (q \rightarrow r)]_0^f \rightarrow [((q \rightarrow p) \rightarrow r) \rightarrow r]_0^f &= 1 \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{2} \end{aligned}$$

Because $[(p \rightarrow (q \rightarrow r)) \rightarrow (((q \rightarrow p) \rightarrow r) \rightarrow r)]_1^f = \bigwedge_{x \in L_3} ([p \rightarrow (q \rightarrow r)]_x^f \rightarrow [((q \rightarrow p) \rightarrow r) \rightarrow r]_x^f)$, we have that $[(p \rightarrow (q \rightarrow r)) \rightarrow (((q \rightarrow p) \rightarrow r) \rightarrow r)]_1^f \leq [p \rightarrow (q \rightarrow r)]_0^f \rightarrow [((q \rightarrow p) \rightarrow r) \rightarrow r]_0^f = \frac{1}{2}$, therefore axiom (A9) is not valid w.r.t. the weak forcing semantic.

$$(A10) \quad \perp \rightarrow \varphi$$

Let us consider $\mathcal{X} = L_3 = \{0, \frac{1}{2}, 1\}$ with the canonical structure of MV_3 -algebra and let $p \in V$ and f a weak forcing property such that $f(p, x) = 0$, for all $x \in L_3$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} [\perp \rightarrow p]_1^f &= \bigwedge_{x \in L_3} ([\perp]_x^f \rightarrow [p]_x^f) = \bigwedge_{x \in L_3} (\bar{x} \rightarrow f(p, x)) = \\ &= (\bar{0} \rightarrow 0) \wedge (\bar{\frac{1}{2}} \rightarrow 0) \wedge (\bar{1} \rightarrow 0) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore (A10) is not valid in the new semantics.

In the same way we can study the behaviour of $|\cdot|_{\mathcal{X}}$ w.r.t. some other formulas of MTL . For example, let us consider the formula $(\varphi \rightarrow \psi) \vee (\psi \rightarrow \varphi)$, where φ, ψ are MTL -formulas. From [Esteva and Godo 2001], we know that this formula is

valid with respect to the truth value semantics. Now, let us consider L_3 with the canonical structure of MV_3 -algebra and let $p, q \in V$. Let us consider a weak forcing property f with the following behaviour w.r.t. p, q :

f	0	$\frac{1}{2}$	1
p	1	1	0
q	1	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$

By definition, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
 [p \rightarrow q]_1^f &= \bigwedge_{y \in L_3} (f(p, y) \rightarrow f(q, y)) = \\
 &= (f(p, 0) \rightarrow f(q, 0)) \wedge (f(p, \frac{1}{2}) \rightarrow f(q, \frac{1}{2})) \wedge (f(p, 1) \rightarrow f(q, 1)) = \\
 &= (1 \rightarrow 1) \wedge (1 \rightarrow \frac{1}{2}) \wedge (0 \rightarrow \frac{1}{2}) = \frac{1}{2} \\
 [q \rightarrow p]_1^f &= \bigwedge_{y \in L_3} (f(q, y) \rightarrow f(p, y)) = (1 \rightarrow 1) \wedge (\frac{1}{2} \rightarrow 1) \wedge (\frac{1}{2} \rightarrow 0) = \frac{1}{2}
 \end{aligned}$$

It follows that $[(p \rightarrow q) \vee (q \rightarrow p)]_1^f = [p \rightarrow q]_1^f \vee [q \rightarrow p]_1^f = \frac{1}{2} \vee \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{2}$.

Therefore this formula is not valid with respect the new kind of semantics.

6 Forcing value of a formula of MTL

In [Montagna and Ono 2002, Montagna and Sacchetti 2004], it was proved that the r -forcing (this notion was introduced also in [Montagna and Ono 2002] and [Montagna and Sacchetti 2004]) is a more adequate notion for reflecting the logical structure of MTL . Arising from r -forcing, we shall define in this section the \mathcal{X} -valued forcing property and forcing value $[\varphi]_{\mathcal{X}}$ of a formula of MTL in a complete MTL -algebra \mathcal{X} . The first one is obtained from an \mathcal{X} -valued weak forcing property $f : (V \cup \{\perp\}) \times X \rightarrow X$ by adding a condition that homogenizes the action of f w.r.t. elements of X . Then one can define the forcing value $[\varphi]_{\mathcal{X}}$, resulting a semantic $[\cdot]_{\mathcal{X}}$ of MTL distinct from $|\cdot|_{\mathcal{X}}$.

One of the main results of the above papers [Montagna and Ono 2002] and [Montagna and Sacchetti 2004] asserts that the Kripke completeness (defined by means of r -forcing) coincides with the usual algebraic completeness of MTL . In this section we shall extend this result, by proving that $[\varphi]_{\mathcal{X}} = \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{X}}$, for any formula of MTL .

We fix a complete MTL -algebra $\mathcal{X} = (X, \vee, \wedge, \cdot, \rightarrow, 0, 1)$.

Definition 12. An \mathcal{X} -valued forcing property is an \mathcal{X} -valued weak forcing property $f : (V \cup \{\perp\}) \times X \rightarrow X$ such that $f(\varphi, x) = x \rightarrow f(\varphi, 1)$, for any $\varphi \in V$ and $x \in X$.

Definition 13. The forcing value $[\varphi]_{\mathcal{X}}$ of a formula φ in \mathcal{X} is defined by

$$[\varphi]_{\mathcal{X}} = \bigwedge \{ [\varphi]_1^f \mid f \text{ is an } \mathcal{X}\text{-valued forcing property} \}.$$

Let f be an \mathcal{X} -valued forcing property.

Proposition 14. For any $\varphi \in \text{Form}$ and $x \in X$, $[\varphi]_x^f = x \rightarrow [\varphi]_1^f$.

Proof. By induction on the complexity of φ .

(1) If φ is an atomic formula, then we apply Definition 12 and we are done.

(2) $[\perp]_x = \bar{x} = x \rightarrow 0 = x \rightarrow [\perp]_1$.

(3) $\varphi = \alpha \vee \beta$. By induction hypothesis, $[\alpha]_x = x \rightarrow [\alpha]_1$ and $[\beta]_x = x \rightarrow [\beta]_1$, hence, by Lemma 3, we get

$$\begin{aligned} [\varphi]_x &= [\alpha]_x \vee [\beta]_x = (x \rightarrow [\alpha]_1) \vee (x \rightarrow [\beta]_1) \leq x \rightarrow ([\alpha]_1 \vee [\beta]_1) = \\ &= x \rightarrow [\alpha \vee \beta]_1 = x \rightarrow [\varphi]_1. \end{aligned}$$

(4) $\varphi = \alpha \wedge \beta$. By induction hypothesis, $[\alpha]_x = x \rightarrow [\alpha]_1$ and $[\beta]_x = x \rightarrow [\beta]_1$, hence, using Lemma 2, (2), it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} [\varphi]_x &= [\alpha]_x \wedge [\beta]_x = (x \rightarrow [\alpha]_1) \wedge (x \rightarrow [\beta]_1) = x \rightarrow ([\alpha]_1 \wedge [\beta]_1) = \\ &= x \rightarrow [\alpha \wedge \beta]_1 = x \rightarrow [\varphi]_1. \end{aligned}$$

(5) $\varphi = \alpha \odot \beta$.

By induction hypothesis, $[\alpha]_u = u \rightarrow [\alpha]_1$ and $[\beta]_u = u \rightarrow [\beta]_1$, for all $u \in X$.

Then $[\varphi]_x = \bigvee_{y,z \in x} (x \rightarrow yz) [\alpha]_y [\beta]_z = \bigvee_{y,z \in x} (x \rightarrow yz) (y \rightarrow [\alpha]_1) (z \rightarrow [\beta]_1)$.

Let $y, z \in X$. Hence, by Lemma 1, (5),

$$x(x \rightarrow yz) (y \rightarrow [\alpha]_1) (z \rightarrow [\beta]_1) \leq yz (y \rightarrow [\alpha]_1) (z \rightarrow [\beta]_1) \leq [\alpha]_1 [\beta]_1$$

Therefore, by Lemma 1, (1), we get

$$(x \rightarrow yz) (y \rightarrow [\alpha]_1) (z \rightarrow [\beta]_1) \leq x \rightarrow [\alpha]_1 [\beta]_1$$

This last inequality holds for all $y, z \in X$, therefore

$$(a) [\varphi]_x \leq x \rightarrow [\alpha]_1 [\beta]_1$$

Particulary, $[\varphi]_1 \leq [\alpha]_1 [\beta]_1$. On the other hand,

$$[\alpha]_1 [\beta]_1 = (1 \rightarrow [\alpha]_1 [\beta]_1) ([\alpha]_1 \rightarrow [\alpha]_1) ([\beta]_1 \rightarrow [\beta]_1) \leq [\alpha \odot \beta]_1 = [\varphi]_1$$

It follows that

$$(b) [\varphi]_1 = [\alpha \odot \beta]_1 = [\alpha]_1 [\beta]_1$$

From (a) and (b) we infer that

$$(c) [\varphi]_x \leq x \rightarrow [\varphi]_1$$

The converse inequality $x \rightarrow [\varphi]_1 \leq [\varphi]_x$ follows easily by

$$x \rightarrow [\varphi]_1 = x \rightarrow [\alpha]_1 [\beta]_1 = (x \rightarrow [\alpha]_1 [\beta]_1) ([\alpha]_1 \rightarrow [\alpha]_1) ([\beta]_1 \rightarrow [\beta]_1) \leq [\varphi]_x$$

(6) $\varphi = \alpha \rightarrow \beta$.

By induction hypothesis, $[\alpha]_u = u \rightarrow [\alpha]_1$ and $[\beta]_u = u \rightarrow [\beta]_1$, for all $u \in X$.

Then, by Lemma 1, (6), we get

$$\begin{aligned} [\varphi]_x &= \bigwedge_{y \in X} ([\alpha]_y \rightarrow [\beta]_{xy}) = \bigwedge_{y \in X} ((y \rightarrow [\alpha]_1) \rightarrow (xy \rightarrow [\beta]_1)) = \\ &= \bigwedge_{y \in X} (xy (y \rightarrow [\alpha]_1) \rightarrow [\beta]_1) \end{aligned}$$

Thus $[\varphi]_x \leq x [\alpha]_1 \rightarrow [\beta]_1$. Particulary, $[\varphi]_1 \leq 1 [\alpha]_1 \rightarrow [\beta]_1$.
 For any $y \in X$, we have $y(y \rightarrow [\alpha]_1) ([\alpha]_1 \rightarrow [\beta]_1) \leq [\beta]_1$, hence
 $[\alpha]_1 \rightarrow [\beta]_1 \leq y(y \rightarrow [\alpha]_1) \rightarrow [\beta]_1 = (y \rightarrow [\alpha]_1) \rightarrow (y \rightarrow [\beta]_1)$
 Therefore $[\alpha]_1 \rightarrow [\beta]_1 \leq \bigwedge_{y \in X} ((y \rightarrow [\alpha]_1) \rightarrow (y \rightarrow [\beta]_1)) = [\alpha \rightarrow \beta]_1 = [\varphi]_1$.
 It follows that
 (d) $[\varphi]_1 = [\alpha \rightarrow \beta]_1 = [\alpha]_1 \rightarrow [\beta]_1$,
 hence $[\varphi]_x \leq x \rightarrow [\varphi]_1$. On the other hand, by using Lemma 1, (7), we obtain
 $x \rightarrow [\varphi]_1 = x \rightarrow ([\alpha]_1 \rightarrow [\beta]_1) = x[\alpha]_1 \rightarrow [\beta]_1 \leq xy (y \rightarrow [\alpha]_1) \rightarrow [\beta]_1 =$
 $= (y \rightarrow [\alpha]_1) \rightarrow (xy \rightarrow [\beta]_1) = [\alpha]_y \rightarrow [\beta]_{xy}$
 Then $x \rightarrow [\varphi]_1 \leq \bigwedge_{y \in X} ([\alpha]_y \rightarrow [\beta]_{xy}) = [\varphi]_x$.
 We conclude that $[\varphi]_x = x \rightarrow [\varphi]_1$.

Corollary 15. *Let f be an \mathcal{X} -valued forcing property. For any $\varphi, \psi \in Form$ we have:*

- (1) $[\varphi \vee \psi]_1^f = [\varphi]_1^f \vee [\psi]_1^f$;
- (2) $[\varphi \wedge \psi]_1^f = [\varphi]_1^f \wedge [\psi]_1^f$;
- (3) $[\varphi \odot \psi]_1^f = [\varphi]_1^f \cdot [\psi]_1^f$;
- (4) $[\varphi \rightarrow \psi]_1^f = [\varphi]_1^f \rightarrow [\psi]_1^f$.

Proof. By the proof of Proposition 14.

For any \mathcal{X} -valued forcing property f , let us consider the evaluation $\lambda_f : V \rightarrow X$ defined by $\lambda_f(\varphi) = f(\varphi, 1)$, for any $\varphi \in V$.

Proposition 16. *For any $\varphi \in Form$, we have $[\varphi]_1 = \hat{\lambda}_f(\varphi)$.*

Proof. By induction on the complexity of φ , according to Corollary 15

If $e : V \rightarrow X$ is an evaluation, then we define the function
 $f_e : (V \cup \{\perp\}) \times X \rightarrow X$ by $f_e(\varphi, x) = x \rightarrow e(\varphi)$, for all $\varphi \in V \cup \{\perp\}$ and $x \in X$.
 By definition, f_e is a \mathcal{X} -valued forcing property.

Proposition 17. *Let $f = f_e$ the \mathcal{X} -valued forcing property associated with the evaluation e . For all $\varphi \in Form$ and $x \in X$, we have $[\varphi]_x^f = x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\varphi)$.*

Proof. By induction on the complexity of φ :

- φ is an atomic formula: $[\varphi]_x^f = f(\varphi, x) = x \rightarrow e(\varphi) = x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\varphi)$;
- $\varphi = \alpha \vee \beta$: by induction hypothesis, $[\alpha]_x^f = x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha)$, $[\beta]_x^f = x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\beta)$.

Then, by using Lemma 2, (4), we obtain

$$[\varphi]_x^f = [\alpha]_x^f \vee [\beta]_x^f = (x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha)) \vee (x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\beta)) \leq$$

$$\leq x \rightarrow (\hat{e}(\alpha) \vee \hat{e}(\beta)) = x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\varphi)$$

By Lemma 3, (2), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\varphi) &= x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha \vee \beta) = x \rightarrow (\hat{e}(\alpha) \vee \hat{e}(\beta)) = \\ &= (x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha)) \wedge (x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\beta)) = [\alpha]_x^f \wedge [\beta]_x^f \leq [\alpha]_x^f \vee [\beta]_x^f = \\ &= [\alpha \vee \beta]_x^f = [\varphi]_x^f \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $[\varphi]_x^f = x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\varphi)$.

- the case $\varphi = \alpha \wedge \beta$ follows similarly;
- $\varphi = \alpha \odot \beta$: by definition and induction hypothesis $[\alpha]_x^f = x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha)$, $[\beta]_x^f = x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\beta)$, we get

$$[\varphi]_x^f = \bigvee_{y,z \in X} (x \rightarrow yz) [\alpha]_y^f [\beta]_z^f = \bigvee_{y,z \in X} (x \rightarrow yz) (y \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha)) (z \rightarrow \hat{e}(\beta))$$

Let $y, z \in X$. Then $x(x \rightarrow yz)(y \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha))(z \rightarrow \hat{e}(\beta)) \leq \hat{e}(\alpha)\hat{e}(\beta)$, hence $(x \rightarrow yz)(y \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha))(z \rightarrow \hat{e}(\beta)) \leq x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha \odot \beta) = x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\varphi)$. It results that $[\varphi]_x^f \leq x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\varphi)$. According to the previous expression of $[\varphi]_x^f$, the converse inequality $x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\varphi) = x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha)\hat{e}(\beta) \leq [\varphi]_x^f$ is obvious;

- $\varphi = \alpha \rightarrow \beta$: by induction hypothesis, $[\alpha]_u^f = u \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha)$, $[\beta]_u^f = u \rightarrow \hat{e}(\beta)$, for all $u \in X$. According to Lemma 2, (2), we can write

$$\begin{aligned} [\varphi]_x^f &= \bigwedge_{y \in X} ([\alpha]_y \rightarrow [\beta]_{xy}) = \bigwedge_{y \in X} ((y \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha)) \rightarrow (xy \rightarrow \hat{e}(\beta))) = \\ &= \bigwedge_{y \in X} (x \rightarrow ((y \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha)) \rightarrow (y \rightarrow \hat{e}(\beta)))) = \\ &= x \rightarrow \bigwedge_{y \in X} ((y \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha)) \rightarrow (y \rightarrow \hat{e}(\beta))) \end{aligned}$$

Thus $[\varphi]_x^f \leq x \rightarrow ((1 \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha)) \rightarrow (1 \rightarrow \hat{e}(\beta))) = x \rightarrow (\hat{e}(\alpha) \rightarrow \hat{e}(\beta)) = x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\varphi)$. Let $y \in X$. Then $y(y \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha))(\hat{e}(\alpha) \rightarrow \hat{e}(\beta)) \leq \hat{e}(\beta)$, hence

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{e}(\alpha \rightarrow \beta) &= \hat{e}(\alpha) \rightarrow \hat{e}(\beta) \leq y(y \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha)) \rightarrow \hat{e}(\beta) = \\ &= (y \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha)) \rightarrow (y \rightarrow \hat{e}(\beta)) \end{aligned}$$

This inequality is true for any $y \in X$, so

$$\hat{e}(\alpha \rightarrow \beta) \leq \bigwedge_{y \in X} ((y \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha)) \rightarrow (y \rightarrow \hat{e}(\beta)))$$

Applying Lemma 1, (7), we obtain

$$x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\varphi) = x \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha \rightarrow \beta) \leq x \rightarrow \bigwedge_{y \in X} ((y \rightarrow \hat{e}(\alpha)) \rightarrow (y \rightarrow \hat{e}(\beta))) = [\varphi]_x^f$$

Proposition 18. *There exists a bijective correspondence between the \mathcal{X} -valued forcing properties and the evaluations of MTL in \mathcal{X} .*

Proof. The assignments $f \mapsto \lambda_f$ and $e \mapsto f_e$ prove the bijective correspondence between the set of \mathcal{X} -valued forcing properties and the set of evaluations in \mathcal{X} .

The following theorem is a consequence of the previous results.

Theorem 19. *For any formula φ of MTL, we have $[\varphi]_{\mathcal{X}} = \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{X}}$.*

Corollary 20. *If the formula φ is provable in MTL, then $[\varphi]_{\mathcal{X}} = 1$.*

7 Final discussion and open questions

We shall discuss two possible directions to extend and improve the results obtained in the previous sections.

7.1 The predicate logic $MTL\forall$ was introduced by Esteva and Godo in the paper [Esteva and Godo 2001]. The language of $MTL\forall$ has the following primitive symbols: variables, predicates symbols, the connectives $\vee, \wedge, \odot, \rightarrow$, the constant \perp , the quantifiers \exists, \forall and the paranthesis $(,)$. The axioms of $MTL\forall$ are those of MTL plus:

- | | |
|---|---|
| ($\forall 1$) $\forall v \varphi \rightarrow \varphi(w/v)$ | (w is substitutable for v in φ) |
| ($\forall 2$) $\forall v (\varphi \rightarrow \psi) \rightarrow (\varphi \rightarrow \forall v \psi)$ | (v is not free in φ) |
| ($\forall 3$) $\forall v (\varphi \vee \psi) \rightarrow (\varphi \vee \forall v \psi)$ | (v is not free in φ) |
| ($\exists 1$) $\varphi(w/v) \rightarrow \exists v \varphi$ | (w is substitutable for v in φ) |
| ($\exists 2$) $\forall v (\varphi \rightarrow \psi) \rightarrow (\exists v \varphi \rightarrow \psi)$ | (v is not free in ψ). |

The inference rules of $MTL\forall$ are modus ponens and generalization: $\frac{\varphi}{\forall x \varphi}$.

The formulas and the sentences of $MTL\forall$ are defined as usual. If D is a non-empty set, then $MTL\forall(D)$ will be the language obtained from $MTL\forall$ by adding the elements of D as new constants.

Let \mathcal{X} be a complete MTL -algebra and D a non-empty set. A first-order \mathcal{X} -evaluation with domain D is a function e from the set $At(D)$ of atomic sentences in $MTL\forall(D)$ into \mathcal{X} . Any first-order \mathcal{X} -evaluation e with domain D can be uniquely extended by induction to a function \hat{e} from the sentences of $MTL\forall(D)$ into \mathcal{X} . The truth value $\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{X}}$ of a sentence φ of $MTL\forall(D)$ in \mathcal{X} is defined as usual [Esteva and Godo 2001, Esteva et.al. 2002].

Now we shall extend the definitions of preceding sections to the new setting. An \mathcal{X} -valued weak forcing property with domain D is a function $f : (At(D) \cup \{\perp\}) \times X \rightarrow X$ such that $f(\perp, 1) = 0$ and, for all $\varphi \in At(D)$ and $x, y \in X$, $x \leq y$ implies $f(\varphi, y) \leq f(\varphi, x)$. In an analogous way we can define the notion of \mathcal{X} -valued forcing property with domain D .

Let f be an \mathcal{X} -valued weak forcing property with domain D . For any sentence φ of $MTL\forall(D)$ and $x \in X$, the element $[\varphi]_x^f$ of X is defined by the conditions (1)-(6) of Definition 5 and the following new clauses:

- (i) If $\varphi = \forall v \psi$, then $[\varphi]_x^f = \bigwedge_{d \in D} [\psi(d)]_x^f$;
- (ii) If $\varphi = \exists v \psi$, then $[\varphi]_x^f = \bigwedge_{y < x} \bigvee_{y < z} \bigvee_{d \in D} [\psi(d)]_z^f$.

Now, for any sentence φ of $MTL\forall$, we can define the weak forcing value $|\varphi|_{\mathcal{X}}$ and the forcing value $[\varphi]_{\mathcal{X}}$ of φ in \mathcal{X} .

For $|\cdot|_{\mathcal{X}}$ and $[\cdot]_{\mathcal{X}}$ we can formulate the following open questions:

Open question 21. Analyse the behaviour of $|\cdot|_{\mathcal{X}}$ and $[\cdot]_{\mathcal{X}}$ w.r.t. the axioms and some other types of sentences in $MTL\forall$.

Open question 22. Compare the semantics $|\cdot|_{\mathcal{X}}$, $[\cdot]_{\mathcal{X}}$, $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{X}}$ and extend the results of Section 5.

The following two propositions constitute a first step in solving the problem 21. We fix a \mathcal{X} -valued weak forcing property f with domain D .

Proposition 23. *Let $\varphi(v)$ be a formula of $MTL\forall$, χ a sentence of $MTL\forall$, $x \in X$ and $a \in D$. Then the following properties hold:*

- (1) $[\forall v \varphi]_x^f \leq [\varphi(a)]_x^f$;
- (2) $[\varphi(a)]_x^f \leq [\exists v \varphi]_x^f$;
- (3) $[\forall v (\chi \rightarrow \varphi)]_x^f = [\chi \rightarrow \forall v \varphi]_x^f$;
- (4) $[\exists v \varphi \rightarrow \chi]_x^f = [\forall v (\varphi \rightarrow \chi)]_x^f$.

Proof.

(1) Obvious.

(2) For any $y < x$, we have $[\varphi(a)]_x^f \leq \bigvee_{y < z} \bigvee_{b \in D} [\varphi(b)]_z^f$, hence $[\varphi(a)]_x^f \leq \bigwedge_{y < x} \bigvee_{b \in D} [\varphi(b)]_z^f = [\exists v \varphi]_x^f$.

(3) By the definition of $[\cdot]_x^f$ and Lemma 2, (2), we get $[\forall v (\chi \rightarrow \varphi)]_x^f = \bigwedge_{b \in D} \bigwedge_{y \in X} ([\chi]_y^f \rightarrow [\varphi(b)]_{xy}^f) = \bigwedge_{y \in X} ([\chi]_y^f \rightarrow \bigwedge_{b \in D} [\varphi(b)]_{xy}^f) = \bigwedge_{y \in X} ([\chi]_y^f \rightarrow [\forall v \varphi]_{xy}^f) = [\chi \rightarrow \forall v \varphi]_x^f$.

(4) Let $b \in D$ and $y \in X$. According to Proposition 8, (4) and the previous inequality (2) we get $[\exists v \varphi \rightarrow \chi]_x^f \leq [\exists v \varphi]_y^f \rightarrow [\chi]_{xy}^f \leq [\varphi(b)]_y^f \rightarrow [\chi]_{xy}^f$. Therefore, for any $b \in D$, we have $[\exists v \varphi \rightarrow \chi]_x^f \leq \bigwedge_{y \in X} ([\varphi(b)]_y^f \rightarrow [\chi]_{xy}^f) = [\varphi(b) \rightarrow \chi]_x^f$. Thus $[\exists v \varphi \rightarrow \chi]_x^f \leq \bigwedge_{b \in D} [\varphi(b) \rightarrow \chi]_x^f = [\forall v (\varphi \rightarrow \chi)]_x^f$.

Proposition 24. *Let $\varphi(v)$, $\psi(v)$ two formulas of $MTL\forall$. Then $[\forall v (\varphi \rightarrow \psi)]_x^f \leq [\forall v \varphi \rightarrow \forall v \psi]_x^f$.*

Proof. Let $y \in X$ and $a \in D$. By Proposition 23, (1), and Proposition 8, (4), we get $[\forall v (\varphi \rightarrow \psi)]_x^f \cdot [\forall v \varphi]_y^f \leq [\varphi(a) \rightarrow \psi(a)]_x^f \cdot [\varphi(a)]_y^f \leq [\psi(a)]_{xy}^f$, hence $[\forall v (\varphi \rightarrow \psi)]_x^f \cdot [\forall v \varphi]_y^f \leq \bigwedge_{a \in D} [\psi(a)]_{xy}^f$. Thus $[\forall v (\varphi \rightarrow \psi)]_x^f \leq [\forall v \varphi]_y^f \rightarrow [\forall v \psi]_{xy}^f$, for each $y \in X$. Therefore, $[\forall v (\varphi \rightarrow \psi)]_x^f \leq \bigwedge_{y \in X} ([\forall v \varphi]_y^f \rightarrow [\forall v \psi]_{xy}^f) = [\forall v \varphi \rightarrow \forall v \psi]_x^f$.

7.2 Recently, a lot of non-commutative fuzzy algebras and their logical calculi were investigated [Cintula and Hájek 2006], [Gottwald 2005], [Iorgulescu 2006a], [Iorgulescu 2006b], [Piciu 2007]. Pseudo *MTL*-algebras (ps*MTL*-algebras, for short) were defined in [Flondor et.al. 2001] arising from the structure of the interval $[0, 1]$ induced by a left-continuous non-commutative *t*-norm.

A ps*MTL*-algebra is a structure $\mathcal{X} = (X, \vee, \wedge, \cdot, \rightarrow, \rightsquigarrow, 0, 1)$, where:

- (C1) $(X, \vee, \wedge, 0, 1)$ is a bounded lattice;
- (C2) $(X, \cdot, 1)$ is a monoid;
- (C3) $x \cdot y \leq z$ iff $x \leq y \rightarrow z$ iff $y \leq x \rightsquigarrow z$;
- (C4) $(x \rightarrow y) \vee (y \rightarrow x) = (x \rightsquigarrow y) \vee (y \rightsquigarrow x) = 1$.

By definition, a ps*MTL*-algebra \mathcal{X} is *representable* if it is isomorphic to a subdirect product of ps*MTL*-chains³ The variety of representable ps*MTL*-algebras is characterized by Kühr's identities [Kühr 2003]:

$$\begin{aligned} (y \rightarrow z) \vee (z \rightsquigarrow ((x \rightarrow y) \cdot z)) &= 1 \\ (y \rightsquigarrow z) \vee (z \rightarrow (z \cdot (x \rightsquigarrow y))) &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

The ps*MTL*-algebras constitute the algebraic base for the propositional calculus ps*MTL*, elaborated in [Hájek 2003a, Hájek 2003b]. An extension of ps*MTL* is ps*MTL*^r, a logical system obtained from ps*MTL* by adding Kühr's axioms:

- (K1) $(\psi \rightarrow \varphi) \vee (\chi \rightsquigarrow ((\varphi \rightarrow \psi) \odot \chi))$;
- (K2) $(\psi \rightsquigarrow \varphi) \vee (\chi \rightarrow (\chi \odot (\varphi \rightsquigarrow \psi)))$.

A standard completeness theorem for ps*MTL*^r was proved by Jenei and Montagna in [Jenei and Montagna 2003], by using a generalization of a technique from [Jenei and F. Montagna 2002].

Two predicate logics ps*MTL*∇ and ps*MTL*∇^r were developed by Hájek and Ševčík in [Hájek and Ševčík 2004] and an weak completeness theorem for the ps*MTL*^r logic was established.

In the framework of logics ps*MTL*, ps*MTL*^r, ps*MTL*∇ and ps*MTL*∇^r we can formulate the following open questions:

Open question 25. Extend the Kripke semantics of [Montagna and Ono 2002, Montagna and Sacchetti 2004] to these non-commutative logics in order to obtain similar standard completeness theorems for ps*MTL*^r and ps*MTL*∇^r.

³ A non-commutative residuated lattice is a structure $\mathcal{X} = (X, \vee, \wedge, \cdot, \rightarrow, \rightsquigarrow, 0, 1)$ verifying the conditions (C1)-(C3) (see [Jipsen and Tsinakis 2002]). Any totally ordered non-commutative residuated lattice is a ps*MTL*-chain.

Open question 26. Define appropriate notions of weak forcing value and forcing value for the logics psMTL , psMTL^r , $\text{psMTL}\forall$, $\text{psMTL}\forall^r$ and obtain non-commutative versions of the results proved in Sections 4 and 5.

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